

Scatter diagram of metroglyph analysis. Tamil Nadu, India.

Entries

- | | |
|--------------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| 1. IET7564 (IRAT8/N22) | 21. IET9817 (Phalguna/TKM6) |
| 2. IET7566 (M63-83/Cauvery) | 22. IET9818 (IR36/K47321) |
| 3. IET7613 (M6383/Cauvery) | 23. IET9819 (IR36/K47321) |
| 4. IET7614 (Rasi/Finegora) | 24. IET9822 (Rasi/Tellavadlu) |
| 5. IET8883 (RP143-4/Phalguna) | 25. IET9823 (M63-83/Cauvery) |
| 6. IET8887 (RP143-4/Phalguna) | 26. IET9824 (Rasi/Ducon) |
| 7. IET8889 (RP1434/Phalguna) | 27. IET9825 (Rasi/Finegora) |
| 8. IET9219 (Rasi/Finegora) | 28. IET9826 (Rasi/Tellavadlu) |
| 9. IET9221 (M63-83/IRAT8//N22) | 29. IET9827 (Rasi/Gajgour) |
| 10. IET9222 (M63-83/RP79-5) | 30. IET9828 (IRAT8/N22) |
| 11. IET9223 (M63-83/RP79-5) | 31. IET9829 (Rasi/Chithiraikar) |
| 12. IET9225 (Mettasanna/Rasi) | 32. IET9830 (IET7614/ARC10372) |
| 13. IET9367 (M63-83/Norin 21) | 33. IET9831 (IET7564/IR50) |
| 14. IET9576 (Phalguna/TKM6) | 34. PM1381 (IR13564/ASD4) |
| 15. IET9809 (Ratna/Zagar) | 35. Rasi (Chandikar/IR8) |
| 16. IET9810 (IR36/Larbyol) | 36. TKM9 (TKM7/IR8) |
| 17. IET9813 (Phalguna/TKM6) | 37. IR50 (IR2153-14-1-6-2/IR28//IR36) |
| 18. IET9814 (Phalguna/TKM6) | 38. TPS1 (IR8/Kattaisamba) |
| 19. IET9815 (IR50/Phalguna) | 39. PMK1 (Co 25/ADT31) |
| 20. IET9816 (IR50/Phalguna) | 40. Nootripathu (local) |

Legend	Score			
	1	2	3	4
Days to maturity	•	•	•	•
Tillers/plant	•	•	•	•
Grains/panicle	•	•	•	•
Root number	•	•	•	•
Root length	•	•	•	•
Root weight	•	•	•	•
Dry matter production	•	•	•	•
100-grain weight	•	•	•	•

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Effect of waxy gene on rice yield components

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We studied the effect of waxy gene on indica rice yield components in 1987, using three pairs of waxy and isogenic nonwaxy lines. (Waxy lines were bred from crosses between their nonwaxy lines and IR29 by Shaoxing Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Zhejiang.)

Seedlings were transplanted at 10- × 18-cm spacing in 1- × 2-m plots, in a split-plot design. Ten plants were sampled from each plot to measure yield components, grain, and rough rice.

Differences in 1,000-grain weight between waxy and nonwaxy lines might be attributed to grain size (see table). Waxy lines have smaller kernels and lower specific gravity.

The potential sink of photosynthates in waxy lines was comparable to that in nonwaxy lines because both had large grains and high percentage of fertile spikelets. The gap between the floral glume and kernel in waxy grain was larger.

Both the lower percentage of rough rice (due to the higher 1,000-hull wt) and the lower specific gravity of grains in waxy lines might make their rough rice yield much lower than expected. □

Characteristics of waxy and nonwaxy isogenic lines.^a Hangzhou, China, 1987.

Character	Guangluai 4			Yuanfengzao			Zhenzhu 19		
	Waxy	Nonwaxy	Difference	Waxy	Nonwaxy	Difference	Waxy	Nonwaxy	Difference
Plant ht (cm)	76.10	75.88	0.22	80.45	78.08	2.37*	93.28	91.43	1.85
<i>Rough rice</i>									
1000-grain wt (g)	21.40	23.08	-1.68**	18.05	19.60	-1.55**	28.30	31.35	-3.05**
Grain length (mm)	6.97	6.80	0.17*	6.19	6.70	0.09	8.70	8.71	-0.01
Specific gravity of grain (g/ml)	0.99	1.10	-0.11**	1.02	1.10	-0.08**	1.04	1.12	-0.08**
Percentage rough rice	78.83	80.15	-1.32**	79.10	80.44	-1.34*	80.74	82.47	-1.73**
<i>Brown rice</i>									
Length (mm)	5.24	5.42	-0.18*	5.13	5.36	-0.23**	6.83	7.13	-0.30**
Width (mm)	2.73	2.89	-0.16*	2.35	2.57	-0.22**	2.62	2.84	-0.22**
Thickness (mm)	1.94	2.03	-0.09*	1.92	1.98	-0.06*	2.06	2.11	-0.05**
Size (mm ³)	27.81	31.83	-4.02**	23.10	26.98	-3.88**	36.80	42.64	-5.84**
1000-grain wt (g)	17.72	20.34	-2.62**	15.64	17.41	-1.77**	23.86	27.50	-3.64**

^a* and ** = significance at the 5% and 1% levels.

Grain quality and nutritional value

Rice varietal differences in number of brokens

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Rice varietal differences in grain form, size, and weight affect percentage of brokens after milling. That determines milling recovery, percentage of head rice, and price.

We measured moisture content of 36 varieties and lines, then hulled 140-g grain samples with a small Satake rubber roll rice hulling machine (THU 35 A). The experiment design was completely randomized with four replications.

Of the varieties tested, 13 had more than 80% head rice (see table). Among them are four lines not yet released—M61b-28-3-5, IR4427-85-2-1, B4180F-30-NG-4-2, and IR4427-5-6-3. IR56 had the lowest head rice percentage.□

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Head rice recovery of 36 varieties and lines.^a Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia, 1985-86 dry season.

Variety	Rough rice moisture content (%)	Brown rice (%)	
		Head rice (%)	Brokens (%)
M61b-28-3-5	13.5	91.4 a	6.7 a
Barito	13.3	86.6 a	7.7 a
IR26	13.3	87.5 a	8.1 b
IR4427-85-2-1	13.5	87.3 a	8.5 b
Semeru	12.3	77.4 ab	10.2 b
Cisadane	13.5	88.0 a	10.3 b
Kelara	15.1	79.8 ab	10.4 b
Bogowonto	14.2	84.7 a	11.7 b
IR46	13.5	85.2 a	12.5 bc
Batang Agam	14.3	84.2 a	12.6 bc
Krueng Aceh	13.2	82.4 a	12.6 bc
Sadang	13.8	84.5 a	12.7 bc
B4180F-30-NG-4-2	13.6	83.4 a	13.8 c
BR319-11-HR12	11.9	77.6 ab	14.4 c
Cipunegara	14.2	82.5 a	14.4 c
M12C-34-3	14.2	78.4 ab	15.7 c
IR4427-5-6-3	12.8	80.3 a	16.2 c
BR-5 1-282-8	14.3	79.1 ab	17.4 c
Citarum	12.4	77.3 b	17.8 c
IR36	12.9	77.7 ab	17.7 c
BR-IRGA-409	13.9	77.6 ab	18.1 c
Cikapundung	14.6	77.7 ab	19.7 cd
GH2 18	14.3	76.2 b	21.0 d
IR4425-85-2-1	14.1	87.3 a	21.2 d
Cimandiri	14.9	72.6 b	21.4 d
B5322b-Pn-1-MS-1-KP-1	14.9	75.7 b	22.2 d
IR5 0	12.5	72.6 b	23.1 d
IR30	11.6	71.2 b	23.3 d
IR22082-41-2	14.1	71.6 b	24.9 d
IR58	13.9	70.3 b	26.5 de
IR28	10.8	68.0 c	26.9 e
IR54	12.8	66.2 c	27.9 e
IR60	12.7	66.9 b	27.9 e
IR5 2	11.9	61.9 c	33.0 e
B40706-NG-2	12.7	61.0 c	35.6 ef
IR56	11.0	53.1 c	44.0 f

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.